

Oxidation of Xylenes by Bismuthoxide-Molybdenum Oxide Catalysts

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Oxidation of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylene on pure bismuth and molybdenum oxides and four mixed oxides of varying compositions were studied. The optimum conditions for oxidation to yield useful products are examined.

MIXED oxides of Bi and Mo are already in use for the oxidative dehydrogenation of butylene to butadiene and manufacture of acrylonitrile from propylene in the presence of ammonia and oxygen. However, less work has been done on the oxidation of aromatic hydrocarbons by them. Oxidation of toluene and ethyl benzene were studied by Adams¹ and oxidation of chlorotoluenes by Chopra and Ramakrishna². We discuss in this paper, results of our work on the oxidation of xylenes on mixed oxides of Bi and Mo.

Experimental

Pure molybdenum and bismuth oxides and four samples (I, II, III, IV) of mixed oxides with varying Bi/Mo ratios were prepared and analysed by standard techniques. They were also characterized by X-ray and infrared analyses. Surface areas of the catalyst were determined by the BET method. The results relevant to the present discussion are given in Table 1.

The xylenes were fractionally distilled and their purity checked by gas chromatography. Oxygen and nitrogen were passed at the required rate through flow meters, mixed in the required proportions, and bubbled through the xylene tube maintained at a given temperature to give different O₂ : N₂ : xylene feed ratios. The total amount of xylene evaporated was measured from the weight

loss in the xylene tube. The gases passed through a preheater kept at 250° and reached the catalyst bed packed with approximately four g. of the sample. The oxidation products were condensed in traps kept in ice and analysed by gas chromatography. Water and carbon dioxide formed during the reaction were absorbed by magnesium perchlorate and ascarite tubes respectively.

Choice of experimental conditions were made after preliminary oxidation runs on sample II. The P_{O₂}/P_{N₂} ratio of ~1 or more was used so as to prevent the reduction of catalysts during the experiment. The space velocity was varied over 0.4-1.3 lit/hr × g. The catalyst temperatures ranged from 250-550°.

Results and Discussion

Blank runs without catalyst in the reaction tube indicated that 15% of the xylene carried into the tube pass through uncondensed in the traps with the exit gases. This was taken into consideration in the mass-balance calculations for subsequent experiments. The oxidation of xylenes by the catalysts proved far from specific. There was a small amount of solid residue condensing on the cooler parts of the outlet tube. The liquid product collected in the trap was a complex mixture of a number of oxidation products. The identification of these

TABLE 1

Sample No.	Bi/Mo atomic ratio	Phases present	BET Surface areas in m ² /g	
			Before sintering	After sintering
Pure Bi-oxide	—	γ- and δ-Bi ₂ O ₃	13.480	6.772
I	2.392 : 1	Bi ₂ O ₃ ·MoO ₃ , Bi ₂ O ₃ *	30.750	11.270
II	1.162 : 1	Bi ₂ O ₃ ·2MoO ₃ + Bi ₂ O ₃ ·MoO ₃	22.790	4.760
III	0.891 : 1	Bi ₂ O ₃ ·2MoO ₃ + Bi ₂ O ₃ ·3MoO ₃ *	24.330	4.745
IV	0.459 : 1	Bi ₂ O ₃ ·3MoO ₃ + Bi ₂ O ₃ ·4MoO ₃	14.520	3.728
Pure Mo-oxide	—	MoO ₃ + traces of MoO ₃ ·s, etc.	17.650	9.355

* Phases present in small amounts.

offered considerable difficulty because the pure compounds were not readily available for comparison. For *o*-xylene, the unconverted xylene itself was the first compound to be eluted out of the chromatographic column, followed immediately by two sharp peaks of the aldehyde and the alcohol. Conversion to these intermediated products was, however, small. The two large peaks with longer retention times were labelled peak 1 and 2 and were identified as the monoacid and phthalic anhydride respectively (Fig. 1). A large proportion of the reactant was oxidised to CO₂ and H₂O. In analysing the results, we took the CO₂ conversion as the index of extreme oxidation as compared to the mild oxidation needed for obtaining desirable products such as product 2 in the chromatogram.

The following conditions were established to be optimum for getting product 2 : P_{O₂}/P_{N₂} = 1 ; partial pressure of *o*-xylene = 0.5 atm ; space velocity 1 lit/hr g ; catalyst temperature = 450°. Table 2 records the results of oxidation of *o*-xylene on the six oxide samples under these conditions. The maximum catalytic activity obtains on sample II with Bi/Mo ~ 1.

The results of oxidation of *p*- and *m*-xylenes under the same conditions are recorded in Tables 3

TABLE 2—OXIDATION OF *o*-XYLENE ON VARIOUS BI-OXIDE-MO-OXIDE CATALYSTS UNDER OPTIMUM CONDITIONS
 Conditions: Catalyst: Bi-oxide-Mo-oxide; Feed: *o*-xylene + (O₂ + N₂) mixture; Catalyst temperature: 450°;
 Ratio, Pressure of N₂: Pressure of O₂: 1:1; Partial Pressure of *o*-xylene: 0.49 atm.

Sample No.	Space velocity lit/hr × g	Weight of xylene fed (g)	Weight of catalyst (g)	% of <i>o</i> -xylene unreacted	% of product 2	% of other products	% of CO ₂	% of total conversion
Pure Bi ₂ O ₃	0.9223	0.7641	3.9172	29.48	6.47	13.37	41.55	61.39
I	1.1280	0.7515	3.0813	—	—	—	30.11	—
II	1.0640	0.7641	3.3941	33.35	16.58	10.60	23.30	50.48
IV	1.1140	0.7542	3.2462	—	—	—	85.75	—
Pure MoO ₃	1.2470	0.3256	2.8982	29.00	10.34	15.32	29.17	54.83

TABLE 3—OXIDATION OF *p*-XYLENE ON VARIOUS BI-OXIDE-MO-OXIDE CATALYSTS UNDER OPTIMUM CONDITIONS
 Conditions: Catalyst: Bi-oxide-Mo-oxide; Feed: *p*-xylene + (O₂ + N₂) mixture; Catalyst temperature: 450°;
 Ratio, Pressure of N₂: Pressure of O₂: 1:1; Partial Pressure of *p*-xylene: 0.56 atm.

Sample No.	Space velocity lit/hr × g	Weight of xylene fed (g)	Weight of catalyst (g)	% of <i>p</i> -xylene unreacted	% of product 2	% of other products	% of CO ₂	% of total conversion
Pure Bi ₂ O ₃	0.8602	0.7854	4.2008	34.65	nil	20.44	34.97	55.41
I	0.9112	0.0154	3.9126	—	—	—	33.44	—
II	1.0640	0.8016	3.3941	45.69	nil	15.17	17.98	33.15
IV	1.1140	0.8001	3.6960	53.37	nil	nil	31.37	31.37
Pure MoO ₃	1.2470	0.8116	2.8982	—	—	—	23.73	—

TABLE 4—OXIDATION OF *m*-XYLENE ON VARIOUS BI-OXIDE-MO-OXIDE CATALYST UNDER OPTIMUM CONDITIONS
 Conditions: Catalyst: Bi-oxide-Mo-oxide; Feed: *m*-xylene + (O₂ + N₂) mixture; Catalyst temperature: 450°;
 Ratio, Pressure of N₂: Pressure of O₂: 1:1; Partial Pressure of *m*-xylene: 0.53 atm.

Sample No.	Space velocity lit/hr × g	Weight of xylene fed (g)	Weight of catalyst (g)	% of <i>m</i> -xylene unreacted	% of product 2	% of other products	% of CO ₂	% of total conversion
Pure Bi ₂ O ₃	0.8602	0.7472	4.2008	50.97	nil	nil	38.63	38.63
I	0.9459	0.7816	3.8202	42.45	nil	nil	41.55	41.55
II	1.0640	0.7412	3.3941	31.25	21.18	9.97	22.81	53.96
IV	1.1140	0.7414	3.2462	34.65	7.40	9.98	33.66	50.34
Pure MoO ₃	1.2470	0.5206	2.8982	—	—	—	23.08	—

and 4. In *p*-xylene, as one might expect, the product 2 was completely absent. The interesting point to note is that in the case of *m*-xylene (Fig. 1) significant amounts of product 2 are formed, particularly with the catalytic sample II. This indicates that demethylation and migration of the methyl groups are taking place on the surface.

Conclusions :

The Bi-oxide-Mo-oxide catalysts are not selective in their oxidation of xylenes. The catalytic activity for useful products is maximum for the sample with

Bi/Mo atomic ratio of ~ 1 . The optimum conditions for oxidation have been established.

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